

ToxSTAR: prediction of drug-induced cholestasis, cirrhosis, hepatitis, and steatosis

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Abstract

Prediction of Drug-Induced Liver Injury (DILI) is still a challenging task. Each indication, including cholestasis, cirrhosis, hepatitis, and steatosis, have distinct underlying mechanisms, making DILI prediction complex. Moreover, drug metabolites, produced through drug metabolism in the hepatocyte, can exhibit varying toxicity profiles compared to the parent drug. To address these challenges, the development of New Approach Methods (NAMs) utilizing in vitro assays and in silico modeling has emerged as a promising solution to enhance DILI prediction. These NAMs leverage advanced technologies to bridge the gaps in traditional toxicity testing and provide more precise evaluations, supporting early identification and mitigation of potential DILI risks.

ToxSTAR offers a user-friendly web interface that enables users to input drug molecules or their metabolites for prediction of drug-induced cholestasis, cirrhosis, hepatitis, and steatosis. It provides (Q)SAR model prediction values based on the molecular structures and hepatotoxicity analysis based on structural similarity between query molecules and drug molecules in the database, which contains in vitro assay and in silico prediction data. At the moment, ToxSTAR is available in desktop version; however, it will be soon released in mobile application (url: <https://toxstar.kitox.re.kr/>)